

Package ‘AMView’

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Title Visualizing AMU Data

Version 1.0-1

Description Visualize AMU data in an interactive Shiny app.

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Encoding UTF-8

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Depends R (>= 4.1)

Imports data.table, bslib, DT, eurostat, htmltools, leaflet, plotly,
shiny, shinycssloaders, shinyscreenshot, shinyWidgets, stats,
utils

Suggests markdown, sf

NeedsCompilation no

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amu_dummy_data *Generate some random artificial AMU data adhering to the variable rules defined by the function am_variables. ATC codes are fetched from the "atc.csv" file in this package, whose source is the Swedish Board of Agriculture. The EntryID is merely an index of the row number.*

Description

NOTE! This function takes quite some time to run for large values of n_rows.

Usage

```
amu_dummy_data(n_rows, start_date, end_date)
```

Arguments

n_rows	the number of rows in the dataset
start_date	The earliest possible date of transaction
end_date	The latest possible date of transaction.

Value

a data.frame with the dummy data

AMView	<i>AMView package imports</i>
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Description

AMView package imports

am_variables	<i>A named list of the variables that go into the common data structure and their types.</i>
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Description

The names of the list elements returned are the variable names defined in the common data structure, and the values can be one of three things:

- Unnamed vector: represents the legal values that that variable can have;
- Empty vector of a given type: defines the legal type of that variable (but the actual value is not restricted);
- Named numeric vector with values between 0 and 1: the names represent the legal values and the numeric value represent the probability with which the values should appear when generating artificial data.

Usage

```
am_variables(varnames = "all")
```

Arguments

varnames	if "all" (default), returns all values. Otherwise returns a subset whose names corresponds to the values given.
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Details

Note that the legal values given here are tailored to be used for generating artificial data using the `amu_dummy_data` function, and to loosely mimic the Swedish cattle sector. The pool of legal values specified here is therefore not universal; see the file under `inst/extdata/content_mapping_AMU.xlsx` for the full specification of the common data structure.

Value

a list as described above.

app	<i>app</i>
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Description

Generate the Shiny app

Usage

```
app(...)
```

Arguments

... additional arguments

Value

a Shiny app object

<code>get_spatial_data</code>	<i>Extract spatial data for a given list of European countries</i>
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Description

Extract spatial data for a given list of European countries

Usage

```
get_spatial_data(country_codes)
```

Arguments

`country_codes` official NUTS country codes for the countries to retrieve data from.

Value

an sf object with the desired geospatial data.

`run_app`*run_app*

Description

Run the Shiny app

Usage

```
run_app(...)
```

Arguments

... additional arguments

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